

Good practice report

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More than ‘pour-and-mix’ – Extending Content Knowledge at the college level through an analysis of coumarin in cinnamon

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Abstract: The article introduces the layout of a college course on analytical chemistry for pre-service teachers. The course aims at fostering teacher students’ professional knowledge by recapitulating *Core Content Knowledge*, introducing *Specialized Content Knowledge*, and complementing it with discipline-overarching *Linked Content Knowledge*. Synthesizing these types of knowledge is expected to support students in their processes of meaning making. As they realize an every-day relevance of analytical chemistry they will see opportunities to relate chemical knowledge to their later school students. Regarding *Linked Content Knowledge*, suggestions are given to address aspects related to the Nature of Science. An exemplary lab activity to analyze the coumarin content in cinnamon is provided. Coumarin has shown adverse health effects in a non-neglectable proportion of humans. Regarding cinnamon there are two varieties of cinnamon with significantly different coumarin content: cassia is very rich in coumarin while Ceylon cinnamon is nearly void of it. The more popular cassia has been shown to be so high in coumarin that a potential risk for light weight consumers cannot be ruled out. Regarding school science, the lab activity can raise an awareness with students for the tentative, creative and socio-cultural Natures of Science – right from the students’ kitchen cabinets.

Keywords: Content Knowledge; Nature of Science; teacher education.

Introduction

Cinnamon is a popular Christmas spice. For some time, advice has been issued to restrict young – i.e., lightweight – children from consuming too many cinnamon-spiced cookies in the Advent season. Regarding German *Zimtsterne* (cinnamon stars cookies, Figure 1), the equivalent of what a child of 15 kg might safely eat has been estimated at 3–6 cookies a day (Abraham, Wöhrlein, Lindtner, Heinemeyer, & Lampen, 2010; Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung, 2012). We asked ourselves, if there was an easy experimental method for schools that could illustrate the coumarin content of (admittedly coumarin-rich) food. An easy analytic procedure has been implemented into pre-service teacher training at the college level where students learn analytic procedures to complement their acquired *Core Content Knowledge* (e.g., Nixon et al., 2019) with *Linked Content Knowledge* which can inform them to better relate chemistry to their students’ lives. The case of *Zimtsterne* appears to be especially striking in this respect as ‘natural’ chemicals are considered hazardous more rarely than ‘synthetic’ chemicals (e.g., Bearth, Siegrist, & Saleh, 2019; Siegrist & Árvai, 2020). Speaking of cookies might, therefore, raise more of an awareness with otherwise disinterested students than lecturing on the physiologically detrimental effects of coumarin-intake.

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Figure 1: Cinnamon stars cookies (source: Pixabay, CC-0).

We suggest employing an ongoing discussion around ‘good and bad’ cinnamon (Dinesh, Leela, Zachariah, & Anandaraj, 2015) to introduce students to some aspects of the Nature of Science (Emden, 2016) as the tentativeness of scientific knowledge as well as the need for creative interpretation of scientific data (cf. Lederman, 2007) clearly surface in the discussion. The socio-cultural Nature of Science (Lederman, 2007) could address economic interest governing to some degree the allowance of a bioactive ingredient into everyday diet.

To do so, the activity needs to combine several types of knowledge from chemistry (e.g., *Core Content Knowledge*: radiation-matter-interaction, nucleophilic reaction mechanisms; *Specialized Content Knowledge*: fluorometry) with *Linked Content Knowledge* pertaining beyond disciplinary boundaries (e.g., medical research and risk assessment). The activity might, thus, be employed in a biology class on health problems as well as in a more traditional chemical analytics course at the college level.

A college chemistry class on analytical chemistry for teachers – why?

The suggested laboratory activity has been implemented in a college course for pre-service chemistry teachers. It is one activity in a semester long course on aspects of analytical chemistry in which students are introduced to several fundamental methods of analytical chemistry in theory and practice. Students are introduced to the underlying chemical principles in a traditional lecture setting (duration: 90 min) with an increased effort at encouraging students to contribute their questions, prior knowledge, and analytical ideas. Students are required to complete a coordinated laboratory activity afterwards (duration: 90 min). Students who take the course are advanced in their studies towards a bachelor’s degree. All the students specialize as chemistry-teachers. They follow detailed instructions during the activities as the course’s aim is not to foster their inquiry skills but to equip them with an understanding of analytical techniques. This relies on an understanding of Scientific Discovery as Dual Search (Klahr & Dunbar, 1988) that implies preparatory familiarity with experimental techniques before one can proficiently experiment (see also Emden & Gerwig, 2020).

Students are not expected to gain an idea of contemporary chemical analysis, which largely works automatically. As reasonable as automation is from an economic point of view, it cannot evoke an understanding of the scientific subject. The researcher typically inserts a test tube, vial, or some similar vessel into some black box, presses some buttons, and waits for the screen to display some results. To operate the machine, the researcher just needs to know when to press which button – the researcher could, essentially, be ignorant of the underlying science on which the black box runs. However, in order to *understand* science, the student – at secondary as well as at the college level – needs to *encounter* the otherwise concealed workings. They must be allowed a peek through the inspection glass of the black boxes, i.e. at best they conduct the analyses on their own. The same rationale perpetuates introducing students to the analytical groups of cationic analysis in college chemistry. Students are supported in learning how ions *generally react* and how to handle apparatus rather than that they are intended to *precisely determine* the composition of a sample. On the

same note, the proposed analytics course employs chemical analyses as a means of conveying and synthesizing chemical Content Knowledge.

The several faces of Content Knowledge

The course's layout has to some degree been motivated by students' unsatisfactory retention of knowledge from their preceding courses, which might be interpreted from an extended view on professional knowledge for teachers. Professional knowledge has traditionally been suggested to comprise Content Knowledge, Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Pedagogical Knowledge (Shulman, 1987). Content Knowledge undoubtedly is essential to developing Pedagogical Content Knowledge (e.g., Abell, 2007) so that lack of the former will negatively affect the latter.

Therefore, it is essential for future teachers to be well educated in terms of Content Knowledge to lay the foundation for their Pedagogical Content Knowledge. This is the distinctive knowledge type of subject teachers, which supports them in selecting appropriate Content Knowledge for their students and which advises them how to convey it to students, i.e., by considering typical student difficulties and by employing suitable methods and scaffolds. At the same time, there has been a growing feeling that Content Knowledge as a concept might be too broad to precisely capture the depth of knowledge needed by teachers: Some suggest distinguishing Academic Content Knowledge (e.g., Gess-Newsome et al., 2019), which typically is referred to in universities, from School-related Content Knowledge (e.g., Dreher, Lindmeier, Heinze, & Niemand, 2018; Hermanns & Keller, 2021) outlining that portion of Content Knowledge typically taught in schools or needed by the teacher to comprehensively understand the compulsory teaching content in the curriculum.

Nixon, Toerin and Luft (2019) introduce three facets of Content Knowledge that do not suggest a hierarchy of knowledges but that progressively widen the scope of knowledge. *Core Content Knowledge* refers to fundamental concepts of a discipline that everybody in it should know (e.g., nature of the chemical reaction, acid-base-theories, models of the atom, etc.). *Specialized Content Knowledge* extends beyond this, describing knowledge that is only needed in select instances of a discipline – laboratory techniques might arguably be subsumed under this heading (e.g., theoretical chemists need not be proficient titrators to do their jobs). Lastly, *Linked Content Knowledge* provides knowledge that allows to relate knowledge between sub-disciplines (e.g., from inorganic and physical chemistry: explaining the precipitation of silver-I-ions with chloride as a function of AgCl's solubility product) as well as beyond the discipline's boundaries. This latter kind of knowledge enables teachers to relate the 'purely chemical' to their students' lives – staying with the example of silver halides, this would have entailed (in a pre-DigiCam era) to bring the processes of black-and-white-photography to the classroom.

The proposed college course aims at (1) recapitulating *Core Content Knowledge* from preceding teaching at college from introductory lectures, (2) at introducing *Specialized Content Knowledge* in the form of analytical procedures, and (3) at equipping students with *Linked Content Knowledge*. This combination of knowledges is intended to result in their synthesis into one coherent application, i.e., students understand the relevance of why and how an analytical approach works. This is decidedly different from the ubiquitous pour-and-mix-recipes frequently found in books on experimentation, where the primary focus is on producing an effect but not explaining what happens (as mentioned above, this kind of black-box-experience cannot be satisfactory when educating teachers). Moreover, *Linked Content Knowledge* provides extra-disciplinary links to help seeing an every-day relevance of the chemical content. This, then, could support students in their later chemistry classes to relate chemistry knowledge to their own students' everyday lives and experiences, which is arguably beneficial to learning (e.g., Childs, Hayes, & O'Dwyer, 2015). Table 1 provides a sketch of how the three types of knowledge complement each other in the course before illustrating the idea in a concrete lab-investigation – entries in the table can only be exemplary and no exhaustive syllabus should be expected.

Table 1: Agenda of analytics course and exemplary aspects of addressed Content Knowledge types.

No. of session	Core Content Knowledge (chemical concepts)	Specialized Content Knowledge (analytical methods)	Linked Content Knowledge
1	Fundamentals of analytic chemistry (measurement, measurement error, precision)	Gravimetry of Fe ³⁺ (with ammonia)	Non-toxicity of contrast agents in radiology
2	Precipitation, solubility product		
3	Analysis of anions (exemplary)	Analysis for Cl ⁻ , Br ⁻ , I ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , NO ₃ ⁻ , S ₂ O ₃ ²⁻	Fractioned precipitation of silver halides
4	Analytical pretests and line spectra (quantum chemistry)	Borax-pearls (Fe ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺), line spectra (Li ⁺ , Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Ba ²⁺), NH ₃ -fumes from NH ₄ ⁺	Fireworks; coloration of glass (e.g., stained glass windows)
5	Analysis of cations (exemplary analytical groups)	Analysis for Al ³⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Fe ³⁺ , Sr ²⁺ , Ca ²⁺	Toxicity of H ₂ S (physiology)
6	Fundamentals of chromatography (solvation, adsorption)	Thin layer chromatography of natural dyes	Achieving six colors for chocolate peanuts from four food dyes
7	Exemplary organochemical tests, analysis of food (preparation of samples; ashing, extracting, etc.)	Analysis of coumarin in cinnamon (fluorometry)	Toxicity of cinnamon (see below)
8	Fundamentals of acid-base-titrimetry and indicators (acid-base-theories, buffers, neutralization)	Alkalimetry of methanolic/ethanolic acid, choosing a suitable indicator	Red cabbage as an indicator
9	Fundamentals of RedOx-titrimetry	Iodometry of ascorbic acid <i>or</i> manganometry of oxalic acid	Physiological effects of increased oxalic acid (kidney stones); dated dichromate-breathalyzers
10	Chemistry of color, fundamentals of coordinative chemistry	Absorption spectra of colored ink	Coloration: d-d-transition vs. polymethine dyes vs. charge-transfer colors
11	Fundamentals of photometry (radiation-matter-interaction)	Photometric determination of Cu ²⁺	Fundamentals of other structure elucidating methods (e.g., IR, NMR, mass spectrometry)
12	Complexometry and eco-analysis	Determination of water-hardness with EDTA	Eco-analytics, pollutants, eutrophication, 'acid' rain
13	Forensic analysis (Marsh's test, toxicity of HCN)	Luminol-reaction using black pudding, Fe ²⁺ and Cu ²⁺ , (human) blood	Myths of crime fiction (Who really can smell bitter almond in HCN? Was Napoleon deliberately poisoned or did the green wallpaper kill him by accident?)

Relating knowledges in the laboratory

The analytics course has been an obligatory element of the curriculum for all students of chemistry at Schwaebisch Gmuend's University of Education since 2017. Students enter the course with generally limited lab skills which they improve throughout the course – judging from their lab reports. Especially, regarding titrations in different activities, it becomes apparent that their care of handling a burette improves, their evaluation of data respects measurement error more pointedly, and more relevant and reasonable sources of error are discussed.

Still, with respect to the suggested lab activity on coumarin in cinnamon, it needs to be noted that some students fail to meet the expected standards: It might happen that samples from cassia are mislabeled or that solutions are contaminated making everything fluoresce. Most students, however, achieve to realize at least a qualitative difference in coumarin contents.

Other researchers choose to augment the Nature of Science (McComas & Olson, 1998; Osborne, Collins, Ratcliffe, Millar, & Duschl, 2003) by, e.g., emphasizing the role of hypotheses and predictions in science, or its gradual development through scrutiny by a peer community. The bulk of alternative suggestions can be paralleled with Lederman’s canon (Neumann & Kremer, 2013). In his earlier approaches to Nature of Science, Lederman focuses the ontology of science by addressing *Nature of Scientific Knowledge*, which only later is complemented by introducing the *Nature of Scientific Inquiry* which devotes itself much more to the epistemological aspects of science (Lederman & Lederman, 2012) – it is the former of these two perspectives that is concentrated on in the following paragraphs.

The college course is not primarily concerned with fostering abilities of scientific inquiry, but some aspects from Lederman’s list dealing with the Nature of Scientific Knowledge can be addressed in the analysis of coumarin in cinnamon (i.e., tentativeness, subjectiveness/creativity, socio-cultural embeddedness). The analytical procedure and its chemistry, thereby, gain an immediate relevance for the students (college and school alike) who might otherwise be less interested in ‘some smelly heterocycle’ that occurs in cinnamon, which they are not too keen on to begin with (“Can’t stand the stench.”) ... learning that there are coumarin-lean cinnamon alternatives and why they are less common might, however, kindle their interest in the odd cookie.

Coumarin in nature and trade – touching the socio-cultural Natures of Science

Sweet clover (*Melilotus alba*), woodruff (*Galium odoratum*) and tonka bean (*Dipteryx odorata*) exhibit considerably high coumarin contents which contribute much to their characteristic odor (the full aroma of, e.g., cinnamon species results from a more complex interplay of at least 20–40 substances (Jayaprakasha, Jagan Mohan Rao, & Sakariah, 2000, 2003; Marongiu et al., 2007; Miller et al., 1995; Senanayake, Lee, & Wills, 1978; Ter Heide, 1972)). Moreover, coumarin occurs in some cinnamon species of the cassia variety.

‘True’ or Ceylon cinnamon (*Cinnamomum verum*) is nearly void of coumarin (Miller et al., 1995) and weak in cinnamaldehyde, which is responsible for the pungent aroma defining cinnamon’s quality (Woehrlin et al., 2010). Cassia cinnamon is the head term for barks from several cinnamon trees: Chinese cinnamon (*Cinnamomum cassia*), Indonesian cinnamon (*Cinnamomum burmanni*), and Vietnamese cinnamon (*Cinnamomum loureioi*). Cassia cinnamon shows high contents of cinnamaldehyde and coumarin (Table 2). Content of components, however, may vary greatly between plant species, between plants of *one* species and even within the *same* plant according to age and/or locus (Woehrlin et al., 2010). Earlier claims of eugenol being absent from cassia or coumarin being found in true cinnamon in traces only (Miller et al., 1995) cannot be maintained according to more recent analyses (Woehrlin et al., 2010).

Coumarin content for woodruff and tonka bean, respectively, may far surpass that of cinnamon (1% of dried mass, 2–3% respectively; Abernethy, 1969). For both these spices, health adverse effects have long been known even to a wider lay public – aromatization of alcoholic beverages with woodruff (e.g., German Maiwein)

Table 2: Components of cinnamon aroma; mean values, standard deviations and range in g/kg.

	Cinnam- aldehyde	Cinnamyl alcohol	Cinnamic acid	Cinnamic acetate	Eugenol	Coumarin
<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> (43 samples)	11.52 (5.19)	0.21 (0.15)	0.09 (0.07)	1.25 (1.05)	0.41 (0.35)	0.03 (0.04)
Range	2.08–28.20	0.04–0.52	0.04–0.25	0.17–4.24	<LOD–8.14	<LOD–0.49
Cassia cinnamon (83 samples)	35.98 (18.62)	0.11 (0.08)	0.66 (0.36)	0.48 (0.38)	0.10 (0.11)	3.53 (2.78)
Range	8.93–76.10	<LOD–0.67	0.09–1.32	0.03–1.11	<LOD–3.65	<LOD–9.90

Compiled data from: Wang, Avula, Nanayakkara, Zhao, & Khan, 2013; Woehrlin et al., 2010; LOD: level of detection.

Table 3: Cinnamon im- and exports; export: top-five exporters and producers (#1, #2, #3, #4), import: top-five importers.

	Rank	Total volume (ground + unground)		<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> (not crushed, nor ground)		Cassia species (not crushed, nor ground)		Ground cinnamon (un- differentiated species)		
		Trade value [kUS\$]	Weight [t]	Trade value [kUS\$]	Weight [t]	Trade value [kUS\$]	Weight [t]	Trade value [kUS\$]	Weight [t]	
Export	Global	661,132	178,283	318,363	51,863	168,998	72,232	171,530	53,816	
	Sri Lanka	#1	202,515	16,617	198,211	16,191	115	6	4190	420
	Indonesia	#2	148,076	50,463	40,431	12,350	28,488	9659	79,157	28,454
	China	#3	109,743	57,184	1342	748	94,761	50,439	13,640	5998
	Vietnam	#4	103,131	25,296	50,665	13,119	33,567	8745	18,900	3432
	Netherlands	#5	20,622	6056	6542	1897	1220	372	12,860	3787
Import	Global	583,958	148,184	294,275	57,598	162,270	63,668	123,057	35,398	
	USA	#1	122,273	34,185	49,099	9333	28,652	9765	44,523	15,087
	Mexico	#2	89,538	n.r.	83,490	6098	1595	207	3517	n.r.
	India	#3	56,916	27,634	5114	886	51,797	26,747	5	2
	Netherlands	#4	19,988	7322	4344	1790	10,373	3703	5271	1828
	Germany	#5	17,311	4825	1034	299	8175	2020	8101	2506

n.r. = no record available; retrieved from: <https://comtrade.un.org> – 29.03.2021 – NB: lines for global statistics are our own summations from tabulated data; differences between export- and import-trade values, -weights respectively, are original.

might frequently result in headaches largely irrespective of the imbibed amount, recipes for preparing dishes with tonka beans usually draw attention to moderate addition of the spice.

Trade statistics for 2017 (Table 3) show that the bulk of traded cinnamon (by mass) stems from the cassia species, while the more expensive Ceylon cinnamon more than outweighs cassia in trade value. The reduced spiciness of Ceylon cinnamon (Blahová & Svobodová, 2012) – due to reduced content of cinnamaldehyde – makes it of lesser interest for the food industry who prefer processing cassia (Vitenskapskomiteen for mattrygghet [VKM], 2010).

This overview shows that, although there have been heated discussions on the tolerance of cassia (see below), it continues to be the dominant species in international trade. This is, on the one hand, due to its relative ‘cheapness’ which allows production of inexpensive consumer goods. On the other hand, cassia gives an improved spice-effect due to its being rich in cinnamaldehyde; i.e., industry needs to add less cassia to achieve a certain spiciness as compared to Ceylon cinnamon. Judging from Table 2, cassia cinnamon should spice equivalently at approximately 1/3 the mass of Ceylon cinnamon. Referring to import values from Table 3, this would come in at an estimated 17% of the cost incurred when adding Ceylon cinnamon. So, there is an indisputable *socio-economic* nature to how scientific knowledge develops. In this instance, it is economy that suggests reading the health-risk-assessments (see below) liberally instead of adopting their production to Ceylon cinnamon or encouraging to culture a new cinnamon species that were rich in cinnamaldehyde and, at the same time, lean in coumarin.

Bioactivity of coumarin – touching the tentative and creative Natures of Science

Coumarin has been discussed as being hepatotoxic (Abraham et al., 2010; Dinesh et al., 2015; Lake, 1999; Ratanasavanh et al., 1996; Woehrlin et al., 2010) and carcinogenic in humans (Abraham et al., 2010; Dinesh et al., 2015; Felter, Vassallo, Carlton, & Daston, 2006; Lake, 1999). The former issue draws on animal studies from which a TDI dose (*tolerable daily intake*) was derived. Based on the NOAEL dose (*no observed adverse effects level*) with beagle dogs, adjusted for interspecies variation (NOAEL x 0.1; since dogs react differently from humans) and intraspecies variation (again x 0.1; since no two humans react completely alike), the advice is to consume no more than 0.1 mg coumarin per kg body weight per day (Anton et al., 2004). The same TDI is

given when incorporating human data from clinical case reports on sensitive humans for whom the NOAEL lies at 5 mg/kg/day (Abraham et al., 2010). The Norwegian Scientific Committee for Food Safety advises an even lower TDI of 0.07 mg/kg/day, drawing on hepatotoxicity studies with rats; this TDI is rarely overstepped in various worst case intake scenarios (VKM, 2010). Other authors (e.g., Lake, 1999) dispute such doses as being irrationally restrictive. They criticize the data basis as irrelevant since it either comes from an intransparent sample of dogs (Felter et al., 2006), or resorts to studies on rats, which show an increased susceptibility to coumarin (Dinesh et al., 2015; Felter et al., 2006) due to a metabolism pathway different from the preferred 7-Hydroxycoumarin-pathway in humans (Felter et al., 2006; VKM, 2010). They, moreover, claim that evidence on human coumarin toxicity is inconclusive but, still, they concede that there is a sensitive subpopulation (Dinesh et al., 2015; Felter et al., 2006). The less susceptible majority, however, could tolerate – according to a conservative estimation relying on rat studies – daily doses of 0.64 mg/kg and probably even exceeded this (Felter et al., 2006).

Observed carcinogenicity by coumarin is not genotoxic in nature, i.e. DNA-reactive behavior has been ruled out for humans (Abraham et al., 2010; Anton et al., 2004; Dinesh et al., 2015; Felter et al., 2006). It is now assumed that carcinogenicity results from organ-specific toxicity (Abraham et al., 2010; Felter et al., 2006). Coumarin or coumarin-containing solutions have even been suggested as remedies in cancer treatment (Lacy & O’Kennedy, 2004) as well as for diabetes mellitus type II (Chen et al., 2012). Regarding the latter, experimental data are inconclusive and intake of these preparations is discouraged (Dinesh et al., 2015); coumarin has been administered for improving blood-flow in small veins despite not showing anti-coagulant activity in contrast to some of its derivatives (Felter et al., 2006; Jain & Joshi, 2012).

These discussions serve to illustrate that data from scientific investigations can be interpreted conflictingly. It always takes the personal perspective of a scientist to make sense of data or to refute the claims by others. There is a *creative* nature to science that cannot be completely separated from the ‘final bit of information’ that is communicated. Moreover, there is no such thing, as a ‘final’ bit – the above sketch shows that health risk assessment of coumarin has changed over time. It is liable to change again if new insights on health-adverse effects of coumarin need to be considered. Thus, scientific knowledge is *tentative* by nature.

Specialized Content Knowledge – the analytic procedure

Samples from cassia are compared with samples from Ceylon cinnamon. A serial dilution of pure coumarin in ethanol-water (4:1) allows for semiquantitative analysis. The analytical approach deviates from the more frequently used thin layer or HPL chromatographies (Sproll et al., 2008) and uses a simplified form of fluorometry (see Haskins & Gorz, 1957).

First, chipped cinnamon sticks (0.5 g) are ground in a mortar with sea sand so that relatively high content of coumarin from unhurt lignin structures (before grinding) might be expected. The grind is suspended in 50 mL of a 4:1 mixture of pure ethanol ($w = 0.96$) with water – do not use denatured alcohol as a solvent since additives, to discourage oral consumption, might show a fluorescence of their own. The suspension is stirred for 30 min (Sproll et al., 2008) and separated by filtration. The filtrate has a light-yellow, clear appearance (Figure 4). Adding one flake of KOH (approximately 0.2 g) to the solution produces precipitation and darkening of the solution (Figure 5). The alkaline reaction is left for 15 min. The forming precipitate is non-definable in composition, but most likely lignin-analogous structures are formed (McFadden & Ross-Morre, 2002). After centrifugation of the suspension, the supernatant is observed under a UV-A-lamp ($\lambda = 365$ nm).

A serial dilution of coumarin in ethanol-water (50, 25, 10, 5 mg L⁻¹ – to 50 mL of each solution one flake of KOH is added) allows an estimate of coumarin content in the samples. Typically, cassia samples yield an intensive fluorescence, while Ceylon cinnamon does hardly/not fluoresce (Figure 6). The intensity of fluorescence with cassia is expected to lie between the 25 and 50 mg-preparations (Figure 7), as the 0.5 g of ‘average’ cassia extracted in 50 mL contain approximately 1.8 mg of coumarin (i.e., 36 mg L⁻¹; see Table 2 – caution: one must not directly compare fluorescence from Figure 6 with that in Figure 7 as both the photographs were taken with different apertures).

Figure 4: Ethanolic solutions of 0.5 g cassia (left) and 0.5 g Ceylon cinnamon (right).

Figure 5: Precipitation after adding KOH; cassia (left), Ceylon cinnamon (right).

Figure 6: Fluorescence under UV-A ($\lambda = 365$ nm), cassia (left), Ceylon cinnamon (right); aperture: 4.5, closure: 1 s.

Figure 7: Fluorescence of dilution series of coumarin in ethanol under UV-A ($\lambda = 365$ nm): 50; 25; 10; 5 mg L⁻¹ (left to right); aperture: 6.3, closure: 1 s.

Fluorescence of the samples increases over time under UV-irradiation so that time of exposition to UV needs to be controlled (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: Comparison of fluorescence of coumarin as a function of irradiation time (t_{irr}) under UV-A ($\lambda = 365$ nm) samples: 0.5 g cassia (left), Ceylon cinnamon (right) in 50 mL methanol: Water (4:1) (aperture: 6.3, closure: 1 s).

Limitations of the analytical procedure

As indicated above, fluorescence cannot be completely ruled out for Ceylon cinnamon. Analogous investigations with extracts of tonka beans may observe a weak blueish fluorescence already with the ethanolic extract which is likely attributable to Umbelliferone (7-Hydroxycoumarin) (Sullivan, 1982). This does not interfere with the dominant fluorescence from *o*-coumaric acid. Neither samples of eugenol (tested with oil of clove diluted to reflect eugenol contents in *Cinnamomum verum*), nor cinnamaldehyde (diluted to reflect average content in cassia, see Table 2) show fluorescence under the given conditions. It is, therefore, assumed that the procedure is specific for coumarin – at least, specific enough for the school science classroom.

Hazards

On principle, the procedure is poor in potential risks. Improved extraction is achieved with methanol ($w = 0.8$) (Sproll et al., 2008) but ethanol has been suggested here to reduce hazards. Ethanol should not be exposed to open flames as it is easily flammable. Flakes of KOH should be transferred with spoons. Students – in college and in schools – should wear protective gloves, safety goggles and a lab coat for the whole procedure. The centrifuge should be loaded equally as to prevent any imbalance in the rotor. UV-A-lamps should be positioned in a manner that make it unlikely for students to look directly into the source.

Conclusion

The proposed laboratory activity can – on principle – be done without any reference to the Nature of Science-aspects referred to in the article. Choosing to ignore Nature of Science when conducting this activity will, however, rob it of its essentials and disconnect the activity from students' experience. It is suggested to emphasize the ongoing dispute about good and bad cinnamon and probe into students' own conceptions of the Nature of Science. One result will be, at any rate, for students to realize that scientific knowledge is inherently ambiguous in its application and, thus, that the scientist's role in uncovering it is much more creative and discursive than is oftentimes imagined.

On a different note, the practical might be exploited in terms of decision-making through benefit-cost-risk-evaluation as one aspect of chemical thinking (Sevian & Bulte, 2015), which needs to be developed throughout secondary school (Sevian & Talanquer, 2014). Students should, thus, be encouraged to evaluate for themselves and make an informed decision which cinnamon they want to use in future. In doing so, students would be enabled to derive an immediate relevance of chemistry for their lives and, thus, to reconnect with an often considered 'off-putting' subject (Childs et al., 2015).

Schwaebisch Gmuend's University of Education students of the analytics course have responded well to the innovative combination of *Core Content* (here: fluorescence of an organical compound) and *Linked Content Knowledge* (here: danger potential of coumarin in cinnamon) as indicated by majorly positive votes in the end-of-term evaluation.

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